

**A SCALE TO MEASURE THE ATTITUDE OF MEMBER
FARMERS OF GRAM PANCHAYAT TOWARDS
PRADHAN MANTRI FASAL BIMA YOJANA**

C. D. Chauhan¹ and J. B. Patel²

¹ Ph. D. Scholar, Dept. of Agricultural Extension and Communication BACA, AAU, Anand-388 110

² Associate Professor, Dept. of Agricultural Extension and Communication BACA, AAU, Anand-388 110

Email : chiragpin237@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Attitude is defined as the degree of encouraging or depressing feeling of the member farmers of gram panchayat towards Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana. Attitude is a way of thinking, acting or feeling of a person towards a situation or cause. It is the accepted fact that an attitude of an individual plays an important role in determining ones behaviour. Keeping this in view a standardized scale has been developed to measure the attitude of member farmers of gram panchayat towards Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana. A summated (likert) rating scale was been developed. The process started with identifying the dimension, collection of items followed by relevancy and item analysis and checking the reliability and validity for precision and consistency of the results. A total of 39 statements were framed in which finally 20 statements were finally retained which has practical applicability in measuring the attitude of the member farmers of gram panchayat towards Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana. The scale contains total twenty statements, out of which twelve are positive and eight statements are negative. The scale developed was found highly reliable.

Keywords: attitude, pradhan mantri fasal bima yojana, gram panchayat, member farmers

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture production and farm income in India are frequently affected by natural disasters such as droughts, floods, cyclones, storms, landslides and earthquakes. Disasters can cause loss of human and animal life, field crops, stored seeds, agricultural equipment/materials, and their supply systems (e.g. infrastructure) as well as associated indigenous knowledge, thus disrupting not only the immediate growing season but also future seasons. Susceptibility of agriculture to these disasters is compounded by the outbreak of epidemics and anthropological (Human caused) disasters such as fire, sale of spurious seeds, fertilizers, pesticides and price fluctuations. All these events severely affect the farmers through the loss in production and farm income and they are beyond the control of the farmers. With the growing commercialization of agriculture, the magnitude of loss due to unfavourable eventualities is increasing day by day. The question is how to protect farmers by minimizing such losses. For a section of the farming community, the minimum support prices for certain crops provide a measure of income stability. Agricultural insurance is considered as an important mechanism to effectively address the risk to output and income resulting from various natural and manmade events. Agricultural Insurance is a means of protecting the agriculturist

against financial losses due to uncertainties that may arise agricultural losses arising from named or all unforeseen perils beyond their control. National Agricultural Insurance Scheme (NAIS), Modified National Agricultural Insurance Scheme (MNAIS), Weather Based Crop Insurance Scheme (WBCIS) were the major insurance schemes implemented in India and due to the various issues of implementation, NAIS and MNAIS have been merged under the single scheme Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) and WBCIS also brought under PMFBY as restructured WBCIS in 2016. The PMFBY is a crop insurance scheme that improved upon its predecessors to provide national insurance and financial support to farmers in the event of crop failure: to stabilize income, ensure the flow of credit and encourage farmers to innovate and use modern agricultural practices. Amongst the methods obtainable for the development of scale, the procedure suggested by Likert (1932) and Edward (1957) was used in this study for scale construction and for ascertaining the response of the scale. The technique selected to construct the attitude scale was "Scale Product Method" which is combination of the technique of Equal Appearing Interval Scale of Thurstone (1946) for selection of the items and Likert's techniques of summated rating for ascertaining the response on the scale. Similar procedure

was also followed by Patel et al. (2013), Patel and Chauhan (2008) Patel and Chauhan (2015) and Vaidya and Chauhan (2008). The following procedure was applied to develop scale. In the present study, attitude referred to the degree of positive or negative affect associated with member farmers of gram panchayat towards the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana. Keeping this in view the present study was designed to develop and standardize a scale to measure the attitude of member farmers of gram panchayat towards Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY).

OBJECTIVE

To develop a scale to measure the attitude of member farmers of gram panchayat towards Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana

METHODOLOGY

Selection of statements

The items making up an attitude scale are known as statements. A statement may be defined as anything that is said about a psychological object. Initially in the procedure of developing the scale, 50 statements were collected from the relevant literature and converted them in context to present requirement. The statements, thus selected, were edited on basis of the criteria suggested by Edward and Kilpatrick (1948) and at last, 39 statements were scrutinized as they were found to be non-ambiguous.

Judges rating on attitudinal statements

In order to judge the degree of 'Agreement' to 'Disagreement' of each statement on the five point equal appearing interval continuum, a panel of 50 judges were selected. The judges selected for the study comprised of extension educationist, and experts of various subjects of social sciences from Anand Agricultural University and other universities. The judges were visited personally with letter of instructions for rating the statements in desired manner.

Calculation of scale and quartile value

The five points of the rating scale were assigned, ranging from 1 for most unfavourable and 5 for most favourable. On the base of judgment, the median value or scale value (S value) and the Q value for the statement concerned was calculated, the inter-quartile range [Q = (Q3 or C75) – (Q1 or C25)] for each statement was also worked

out for determination of ambiguity involved in the statement. Following formulas were applied to work out S, Q3 and Q1 values.

$$\text{S or Median Value} = L + \frac{(0.50 - \sum pb)}{Pw} \times i$$

Where,

S = Median or Scale value of statement

L = Lower limit of the interval in which the median falls

$\sum pb$ = Sum of the proportion below the interval in which the median falls

Pw = Proportion within the interval in which the median falls

I = Width of the interval which was assumed as equal to 1.0.

$$C_{25} \text{ or } Q_1 = L + \frac{(0.25 - \sum pb)}{Pw} \times i$$

Where,

C₂₅ = the 25th centile

L = Lower limit of the interval in which the median falls

$\sum pb$ = Sum of proportion below the interval in which the 25th centile falls

Pw = Proportion within the interval in which the 25th centile falls

i = Width of the interval which was assumed as equal to 1.0.

$$C_{75} \text{ or } Q_3 = L + \frac{(0.75 - \sum pb)}{Pw} \times I$$

Where,

C₇₅ = the 75th centile value of the statement

L = Lower limit of the interval in which the median falls

$\sum pb$ = Sum of proportion below the interval in which the 75th centile falls

Pw = Proportion within the interval in which the 75th centile falls

i = Width of the interval which was assumed as equal to 1.0.

Table 1: Discrimination of items on the bases of S and Q values

Statement Number	Statements	S value	Q value	Decision
11	Opting insurance under PMFBY is stressful for me	3.25	2.20	Accepted
7	PMFBY insurance scheme is of poor quality	3.06	2.89	Rejected
29	Crop Insurance scheme is not in reach of marginal farmers	3.06	2.46	Accepted
5	I feel that availing of PMFBY is time consuming	3.00	2.22	Accepted
20	I feel that crop insurance is only for big farmers	2.88	2.61	Rejected
28	I feel that mostly educated farmers are getting benefits from PMFBY	2.88	2.54	Accepted
6	In my opinion getting PMFBY is wastage of money	2.77	2.61	Rejected
18	Long distance in availing PMFBY discourage me to adopt	2.72	2.04	Accepted
22	Getting compensation in PMFBY scheme is time consuming	2.43	1.22	Accepted
33	I believe that PMFBY is more propaganda than reality	2.43	2.28	Rejected
31	I feel difficult in availing crop insurance	2.43	2.32	Rejected
26	I believe that PMFBY scheme is more business oriented	2.39	1.46	Accepted
27	PMFBY scheme is not useful to illiterate famers	2.39	3.01	Rejected
30	I feel that political interventions are more in PMFBY	2.36	1.94	Accepted
14	I feel that crop insuring agency are not compensating fairly	2.33	1.73	Accepted
10	I feel that Insuring agencies exploits with high premium charges	2.32	1.78	Rejected
4	Availing of PMFBY insurance would improve my social status in my community	2.29	1.27	Accepted
37	I feel that PMFBY helps in interacting with different institutions	2.29	1.64	Rejected
17	I believe that all insurance claims are handled within the expected time	2.28	1.86	Rejected
15	I am satisfied with the agencies of crop insurance scheme	2.18	1.70	Rejected
34	PMFBY has low premium rate compared to previous crop insurance schemes	2.17	0.58	Accepted
16	Crop Insurance makes easier to obtain loan from banks	2.15	1.76	Rejected
21	Adoption of PMFBY indicates scientific orientation	2.15	1.70	Accepted
13	PMFBY helps me in protecting the fluctuations of production in future	2.04	1.15	Rejected
32	I am satisfied with the handlings of crop insurance services	2.04	2.12	Rejected
38	PMFBY helps in maintaining economic condition in drought situation	2.02	1.04	Accepted
35	PMFBY programme is more government friendly approach	2.00	1.72	Rejected
36	PMFBY programme is more farmers friendly approach	2.00	1.77	Rejected
12	Crop insurance helps me to go for adoption of crop diversification	1.98	1.16	Accepted
23	I believe that PMFBY scheme has become a real boon to farmers	1.91	0.88	Accepted
39	It is good to adopt crop insurance because it can provide a happy secured life	1.91	1.58	Rejected
8	I would be able to cope up with risks better by using crop insurance scheme	1.91	0.98	Rejected
2	PMFBY helps to stabilize the income	1.84	1.24	Accepted
25	I believe that PMFBY scheme is more welfare oriented	1.87	0.97	Accepted
19	I would like to continue crop insurance scheme as it saves me from risk	1.80	1.44	Rejected

Statement Number	Statements	S value	Q value	Decision
9	PMFBY Crop insurance helps me at the time of repayment of losses	1.80	1.59	Rejected
3	I believe that PMFBY is able to encourage me to adopt innovative agricultural practices	1.80	1.35	Accepted
24	PMFBY scheme is essential for the economic growth of famers	1.75	1.25	Accepted
1	I believe that PMFBY helps me to protect against financial risks	1.33	1.03	Accepted

Table 2: Final selected statements for the scale to measure attitude of member farmers of gram panchayat towards PMFBY

Sr. No.	Statements	SA	A	UD	DA	SDA
1	I believe that PMFBY helps me to protect against financial risks (+)					
2	PMFBY helps to stabilize the income (+)					
3	I believe that PMFBY is able to encourage me to adopt innovative agricultural practices (+)					
4	Availing of PMFBY insurance would improve my social status in my community (+)					
5	I feel that availing of PMFBY is time consuming (-)					
6	Opting insurance under PMFBY is stressful for me (-)					
7	Crop insurance helps me to go for adoption of crop diversification (+)					
8	I feel that crop insuring agency are not compensating fairly (-)					
9	Long distance in availing PMFBY discourage me to adopt (-)					
10	Adoption of PMFBY indicates scientific orientation (+)					
11	Getting compensation in PMFBY scheme is time consuming (-)					
12	I believe that PMFBY scheme has become a real boon to farmers (+)					
13	PMFBY scheme is essential for the economic growth of famers (+)					
14	I believe that PMFBY scheme is more welfare oriented (+)					
15	I believe that PMFBY scheme is more business oriented (+)					
16	I feel that mostly educated farmers are getting benefits from PMFBY (-)					
17	Crop Insurance scheme is not in reach of marginal farmers (-)					
18	I feel that political interventions are more in PMFBY (-)					
19	PMFBY has low premium rate compared to previous crop insurance schemes (+)					
20	PMFBY helps in maintaining economic condition in drought situation (+)					

Final statements for attitude scale

When there was a good agreement among the judges, in judging the degree of agreement or disagreement of a statement, Q was smaller compared to the scale value obtained. Thus, only those statements were selected whose median (scale) values were greater than Q values. However, when a few statements had the more or less similar scale values, statements having lowest Q value were selected. Based on the median and Q values, 20 statements numbering 11, 5, 28, 18, 22, 26, 30, 14, 4, 34, 21, 38, 12, 25, 3, 24, and 1 of a schedule were finally selected to measure the attitude of member farmers of gram panchayat towards PMFBY

Reliability of the scale

A scale is reliable when it gives consistently same results when it applied to the same sample. The designed

attitude scale for the study was tested for its reliability by using the split half method. It was introduced to 30 respondents of non-sample area. The coefficient of reliability between these two sets of score was calculated by Rulon’s formula (Guilford 1954), which came to 0.766 Thus the scale developed was highly reliable.

Thus the correction factor is calculated by using Spearman Brown formula

Where,

rtt = Coefficient of the reliability of the original test

roe = reliability of coefficients of odd and even score

The coefficient of reliability was calculated by the Spearman Brown formula which came to be 0.867. Thus, the scale developed was found highly reliable.

Content validity of the scale

The content validity of the scale was tested. It is the representative or sampling adequacy of the content, the substance, the matter and the topics of a measuring instrument. This method was used in the present scale to determine the content validity of the scale. As the content of the attitude was thoroughly covered the subject matter under the study through literature and expert opinion, it was assumed that present scale satisfied the content validity.

Scoring system

The responses of the selected 10 statements can be collected on five points continuum viz. strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree with respective weights of 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1 for the favourable statements and with the respective weights of 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 for the unfavourable statements.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The final scale was called to be the standardized one which consisted of 20 statements. The scale developed to measure attitude of member farmers of gram panchayat towards PMFBY where responses had to be recorded on a five point continuum representing strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree with scores of 5, 4, 3, 2, and 1, respectively. The attitude score of each respondent can be calculated by adding up the scores.

CONCLUSION

The attitude scale developed was found to be reliable and valid. The attitude scale developed was administered on 30 member farmers of gram panchayat of a non-sample area, there were no complications in using the scale, hence it can be concluded that the scale developed was useful in measuring the attitude towards PMFBY. Hence, researchers can use this

scale in future for measuring the attitude of farmers in the similar studies.

REFERENCES

- Edward, A. L. (1957). Techniques of attitude scale construction. Vakils, Feffer and Simons Pvt. Ltd. Bombay – 1.
- Guilford, J. P. (1954). Psychometric Methods. Tata McGraw-Hill Publication Co. Ltd., Bombay, pp: 378-382.
- Kishan K., Chauhan N. B., & Patel J. B. (2016). Development of scale to measure attitude of the farmers towards neem based bio pesticides, *International Journal of Agriculture Sciences*, 8(21), 1394-95.
- Likert, R. A. (1932). A technique for the measurement of attitude scales. Arch. Psychol. New York, No.140.
- Patel, J. K., Patel, J. B., Onima, V. T., & Chauhan, N. B. (2013). Development of Scale to Measure Attitude of Farmers towards Holstein Friesian, *Guj. J. Ext. Edu.* 24, 1-3. <http://www.gjoe.org/papers/197.pdf>
- Patel, M. C. & Chauhan, N. B. (2015). Development of Scale to Measure Attitude Towards Farmer's Training Programmes Organized by SAUs of Gujarat State, *Guj. J. Ext. Edu.* 26(1), 1-3.
- Patel, M. C. & Chauhan, N. B., (2008). A scale to measure attitude of research scholars towards use of Information technology for their empowerment. *Agric. Sci. Digest.*, 28, 286-288.
- Thurstone, L. L. (1946). The Measurement of attitude *American J. of Sociology*. Chicago University Press, 39-50.
- Vaidya, A. C. & Chauhan, N. B. (2008). Scale to Measure Attitude of Farmers towards Poultry Farming, *Guj. J. Extn. Edu.* 19, 15-17.